

NONLINEAR ANALYSIS OF A MINIMUM-WEIGHT EQUIVALENT COMPOUND CYLINDER

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ABSTRACT

This paper covers a nonlinear analysis of a compound tube constructed of a steel liner and a composite outer jacket. The compound tube achieves the maximum weight reduction and has the same bore displacement per unit of internal pressure in the lightweight design as in the original design of monoblock steel tube. The composite jacket is elastically orthotropic and the maximum strain failure criterion is used. The steel liner is assumed to obey Tresca's yield criterion, its associated flow theory, and the linear strain-hardening rule. Analytical solutions are obtained for all loading ranges up to failure.

Keywords: Compound Tube, Composite Jacket, Nonlinear Analysis, Residual Stress, Failure, Design Methodology

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composites have become familiar structural components in many applications that require high stiffness and low weight. This situation also exists in a current problem with Army cannon. We would like to design longer cannon using composite materials, while still maintaining the inertia characteristics of the shorter cannon. The design under consideration is to replace a portion of the thick-walled cylinder with a lighter material. The inner portion, the steel liner, maintains the tube projectile interface and shields the composite from the extremely hot gases. The outer portion, the composite jacket, is made of fiber-reinforced organic composite or metal matrix composite materials. Steel liners wrapped with single or multilayered organic composites were fabricated and tested [1]. Analytical nonlinear solutions including residual stresses were presented [2].

In a recent paper [3], Witherell presented a method to design a minimum-weight equivalent compound cylinder (ECC). The compound cylinder achieves the maximum weight reduction and has the same bore displacement per unit of internal pressure in the lightweight design as in the original design of isotropic monoblock cylinder (IMC). This paper covers a nonlinear analysis of such a minimum-weight ECC. Stress analyses beyond the elastic limit are emphasized in the investigation. Elastic-plastic, fully-plastic, unloading, and failure analyses are included. The composite jacket is elastically orthotropic and the maximum strain failure

criterion is used. The steel liner is assumed to obey the Tresca's yield criterion, its associated flow theory, and the linear strain-hardening rule. Analytical expressions for the stresses and displacements in the ECC are developed for the complete ranges of loadings up to failure. Numerical results for the stresses and displacements in the ECC are presented as functions of internal pressure. The distributions of hoop stresses before and after complete unloadings are also shown.

2. EQUIVALENT COMPOUND CYLINDER

An IMC of inner radius 'a' and outer radius 'b_o' can be made lighter by replacing its outer portion with a lightweight stiff composite material such that the resulting compound cylinder has a bore radial displacement (per unit of internal pressure) equivalent to that of the original isotropic design [3]. This ECC consists of an isotropic liner of inner radius 'a' and outer radius 'b' and a composite jacket of inner radius 'b' and outer radius 'c'. Both the liner and IMC are made of the same isotropic material characterized by Young's modulus E, Poisson's ratio, and density d. The composite jacket is constructed from a cylindrically-orthotropic material and has a density d_j. Since only internal pressure loading 'p' is considered, shear effects are eliminated, and the number of material constants necessary for the analysis reduces to six: three Young's moduli, E_r, E_θ, E_z, and three Poisson's ratios, ν_{rθ}, ν_{θz}, and ν_{rz}. The r, θ, and z, subscripts correspond to the radial, hoop, and axial directions in the cylindrical coordinate system. The Poisson's ratio ν_{ij} is defined as the strain ratio ε_j/ε_i when a stress in the i-direction is applied. The other three Poisson's ratios can be determined by taking account of the symmetry in the compliance matrix; e.g., E_rν_{θr} = E_θν_{rθ}.

The linear analysis for the compound cylinder in the plane-strain condition gives an explicit expression for the bore displacement per unit of internal pressure u_a/p as,

$$\left(\frac{b^2}{a^2}-1\right)\frac{E}{p}\frac{u_a}{a} = (1+\nu)\frac{b^2}{a^2} + (1-\nu-2\nu^2) - \frac{4(1-\nu^2)(b^2/a^2)}{\left(\frac{b^2}{a^2}-1\right)\left[\frac{Ak(c/b)^{2k+1}+B}{(c/b)^{2k-1}}\right]+\frac{b^2}{a^2}+1} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} k &= (\alpha_{11}/\alpha_{22})^{1/2}, & a_{11} &= (1-\nu_{rz}\nu_{zr})/E_r, & \alpha_{12} &= (\nu_{\theta r}+\nu_{\theta z}\nu_{zr})/E_{\theta}, \\ \alpha_{22} &= (1-\nu_{\theta z}\nu_{z\theta})/E_{\theta}, & A &= E\alpha_{22}/(1-\nu^2), & B &= -E\alpha_{12}/[(1-\nu^2)-\nu/(1-\nu)] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Lamé's solution for the IMC gives the corresponding expression

$$(b_0^2/a^2-1)(E/p)(u_a/a) = (1+\nu)b_0^2/a^2+(1-\nu-2\nu^2) \quad (3)$$

If the compound cylinder is made equivalent to the original IMC by requiring u_a/p to be the same for both cases, then we obtain an equation defining the wall ratio 'c/b' of the composite jacket by

$$(c/b)^{2k} = \frac{1+kA-B}{(1-kA-B)} + \frac{R^2(1-kA+B)}{R^2(1+kA+B)} \equiv \frac{N}{D} \quad (4)$$

where R = b/b_o and α = a/b_o < R < 1. The weight ratio 'w' of the ECC replacing an IMC can be expressed as a function of R for a specific α and known material properties by

$$w = [R^2(1-1/F) - \alpha^2 + (R^2/F)(N/D)^{(1/k)}]/(1-\alpha^2) \quad (5)$$

where $F = d/d_j$. Taking the derivative of w with respect to R and setting it equal to 0, we have an equation

$$4AR^2 - ND - (F-1)(ND)(D/N)^{(1/k)} = 0 \quad (6)$$

which defines the value of R that produces the minimum value of the weight ratio. It is interesting to point out that this critical value of R depends only on the material properties.

3. ELASTIC-PLASTIC ANALYSIS

The elastic solution for a compound cylinder subjected to small internal pressure is well known. All the stresses and displacements can be determined as linear functions of internal pressure p . When the internal pressure p is large enough, part of the steel liner will become plastic. Using Tresca's yield criterion, the associated flow rule, and assuming linear strain-hardening, the nonlinear elastic-plastic solution can be obtained in closed form [4]. Using the requirement of displacement continuity at the interface, we can obtain the expression for the interface pressure q as

$$\frac{q}{\sigma_o} = \frac{(1-\nu^2)\rho^2/b^2}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu) + E \left[\alpha_{22}k \frac{(c/b)^{2k+1}}{(c/b)^{2k}-1} - \alpha_{12} \right]} \quad (7)$$

where σ_o is the initial yield stress and ρ locates the elastic-plastic interface in the liner. Given any value of ρ in $a < \rho < b$, we can now determine q , u , and all the stresses in the liner and jacket. The expressions for the displacement, radial, and hoop stresses in the liner are given below, in the elastic portion ($\rho \leq r \leq b$):

$$(E/\sigma_o)u/r = \frac{1+\nu}{2} \rho^2/r^2 + (1-\nu-2\nu^2)^{1/2}(\rho^2/b^2 - q/\sigma_o) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_r/\sigma_o}{\sigma_\theta/\sigma_o} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\mp \frac{\rho^2}{r^2} + \frac{\rho^2}{b^2} \right) - \frac{q}{\sigma_o} \quad (9)$$

and in the plastic portion ($a \leq r \leq \rho$):

$$(E/\sigma_o)u/r = (1-\nu-2\nu^2)\sigma_r/\sigma_o + (1-\nu^2)\rho^2/r^2 \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_r/\sigma_o}{\sigma_\theta/\sigma_o} = \mp \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \eta\beta + \eta\beta \frac{\rho^2}{r^2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\rho^2}{b^2} - (1-\eta\beta) \ln \frac{\rho}{r} - \frac{q}{\sigma_o} \quad (11)$$

where

$$\eta = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \frac{E}{\sigma_o} \frac{m}{1-m}, \quad \eta\beta = \frac{m}{m + \frac{3(1-m)}{4(1-\nu)^2}}$$

$$\sigma = \sigma_o(1+\eta\epsilon^p), \quad \bar{\epsilon}^p = \beta(\rho^2/r^2-1), \quad m = E_t/E \quad (12)$$

and E_t is the tangent modulus in the plastic range of the stress-strain curve. By letting $\rho = a$ and b , we can determine the lower limits p^* , q^* , u_a^* and the upper limits p^{**} , q^{**} , u_a^{**} , respectively.

4. FULLY-PLASTIC ANALYSIS

When the internal pressure p is further increased, i.e., $p > p^{**}$, the steel liner will become fully-plastic. The composite jacket remains elastic as long as the failure pressure is not reached. Using Tresca's yield criterion, the associated flow rule, and assuming linear strain-hardening, a fully-plastic solution can still be obtained [2]. The explicit expressions for the displacement and stresses in the plane-strain case are

$$ru = E^{-1}(1-2\nu)(1+\nu)r^2\sigma_r + \phi b^2 \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_r = -p + \sigma_o(1-\eta\beta)\ln\left(\frac{r}{a}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\eta\beta}{(1-\nu^2)} \left[\frac{b^2}{a^2} - \frac{b^2}{r^2} \right] E\phi \quad (14)$$

$$\sigma_\theta = \sigma_r + \sigma_o(1+\eta\bar{\epsilon}^p) \quad (15)$$

where σ_o , η , and $\bar{\epsilon}^p$ are the initial yield stress, hardening parameter, and equivalent plastic strain, respectively, and

$$\bar{\epsilon}^p = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \left[\phi \frac{b^2}{r^2} - (1-\nu^2)\sigma_o/E \right] \left[1 + \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}(1-\nu^2)\eta\sigma_o/E \right] \quad (16)$$

$$\phi = \left[E\alpha_{22}k \frac{(c/b)^{2k+1}}{(c/b)^{2k-1}} - E\alpha_{12} + (1-2\nu)(1+\nu) \right] q/E \quad (17)$$

$$p = \sigma_o(1-\eta\beta)\ln\frac{b}{a} + q \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{2}\eta\beta \left(\frac{b^2}{a^2} - 1 \right) \left[Ak \frac{(c/b)^{2k+1}}{(c/b)^{2k-1}} + B + 1 \right] \right\} \quad (18)$$

5. UNLOADING ANALYSIS

If the pressure p is subsequently removed completely with no reverse yielding, the unloading is entirely elastic and the solution, denoted by a prime, is given by

$$q' = 2p' \left/ \left(\frac{b^2}{a^2} - 1 \right) \right. \left[Ak \frac{(c/b)^{2k+1}}{(c/b)^{2k-1}} + B \right] + \frac{b^2}{a^2} + 1 \quad (19)$$

$$\left. \begin{matrix} \sigma_r' \\ \sigma_\theta' \end{matrix} \right\} = \left\{ \mp (p' - q') \left(\frac{b}{r} \right)^2 + p' - q' \frac{b^2}{a^2} \right\} \left/ \left(\frac{b^2}{a^2} - 1 \right) \right. \quad (20)$$

$$U'/r = E^{-1}(1+\nu)[(p'-q')(b/r)^2 + (1-2\nu)(p'-q' b^2/a^2)](b^2/a^2 - 1) \quad (21)$$

The residual state stress system, denoted by two primes, is the sum of the system produced by loading and that produced by unloading, i.e., $\sigma_\theta'' = \sigma_\theta + \sigma_\theta'$, etc. Assuming no Bauschinger effect and using Tresca's yield criterion subject to $\sigma_r'' > \sigma_z'' > \sigma_\theta''$, the reverse yielding will not occur if

$$\sigma_r'' - \sigma_\theta'' \leq \sigma'' = \sigma_n[1+m\xi/(1-m)] \quad (22)$$

The unloading solution considering reverse yielding, but neglecting the Bauschinger effect, was first obtained by Bland [6]. If we need to consider the Bauschinger effect during unloading, analytical solutions given in [5] can be used.

6. FAILURE ANALYSIS

The steel is assumed to be elastic-plastic, linear-hardening with $\sigma_o = 826.8$ MPa, $E_t = 826.8$ MPa, and σ_u (ultimate strength) = 964.6 MPa. The steel liner is considered as failure when the maximum yield stress reaches the ultimate limit (σ_u). The composite jacket is elastically-orthotropic, and brittle failure is considered with the maximum strain criterion [6]. The maximum strain from each simple test is either measured or computed from the measured strength divided by the elastic modulus. For the composite jacket used here, the maximum strain criterion is

$$-\epsilon_x'^* \leq \epsilon_\theta \leq \epsilon_x^* \quad \text{and} \quad -\epsilon_y'^* \leq \epsilon_r \leq \epsilon_y^* \quad (23)$$

where $\epsilon_x^* = X/E_\theta$, $\epsilon_x'^* = X'/E_\theta$, $\epsilon_y^* = Y/E_r$, $\epsilon_y'^* = Y'/E_r$ and $X, X', Y, Y' = 1805, 1550, 60, 150$ MPa, respectively.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

If we consider an IMC made of steel with $E = 206.7$ GPa, $\nu = 0.3$, $d = 7.6$ g/cc, and a composite replacement material of an all-hoop wrap IM6/bismaleimide (55 percent fiber volume ratio) with $E_r = E_z = 7.758$ GPa, $E_\theta = 160.61$ GPa, $\nu_{r\theta} = 0.01524$, $\nu_{\theta z} = 0.3155$, $\nu_{rz} = 0.3991$, $d_c = 1.52$ g/cc, then the solution of Eq. (6) gives the critical value of $R_{cr} = 0.88073$, and $c/b = 1.27071$ with the aid of Eq. (4). To replace a steel IMC with $a = 2.286$ cm, $b_0 = 3.02$ cm, a minimum-weight design of the ECC using the above composite material would require $b = 2.66$ cm and $c = 3.38$ cm. The minimum value of the weight ratio 'w' according to Eq. (5) is 70 percent, i.e. the maximum weight reduction is 30 percent. The numerical results of stresses and strains for such a minimum-weight ECC have been obtained for all loading ranges including elastic, elastic-plastic, fully-plastic, unloading, and failure.

Figure 1 shows the radial displacement or hoop strain at the bore as a function of internal pressure for both cylinders, i.e., the minimum-weight ECC and the steel IMC. The results in the linear range for the minimum-weight ECC are identical to the original design of IMC. The results in the elastic-plastic range are still close, but the relations in the fully-plastic range are quite different as shown in the figure. The hoop strains at the interface and the outside surface of the ECC are also shown in Figure 1. The complete ranges of loadings up to failure have been considered. The maximum value of internal pressure that this ECC can contain without failure is $p_f = 448$ MPa, and the maximum strain in the composite is 1.12 percent. The lightweight design is much safer because the failure pressure for the original steel IMC is only about 260 MPa. The results of interface pressure q , hoop stresses at the bore (σ_θ/a), and interfaces ($\sigma_\theta/b-$ and $\sigma_\theta/b+$) are shown in Figure 2 as functions of internal pressure. It should be noted that the hoop stresses at the interface are discontinuous with $b-$ and $b+$ representing the location in the liner and jacket, respectively. Figure 2 shows very clearly that the results change drastically when yielding occurs. The relation changes from linear to nonlinear when yielding sets in, and a more significant change occurs when the fully-plastic state is reached. The distribution of hoop stresses in the liner and jacket can be obtained at any given value of internal pressure. If the pressure p is subsequently removed completely, the residual displacements, strains, and stresses can be obtained. In Figure 3 we present the stress distributions before and after unloading from four values of internal pressure, i.e., $p = 176.6, 219.3, 248.7, 277.9$ MPa. The first three values correspond to initial yielding, 50 percent yielding, and 100 percent yielding, respectively. The percent yielding in the elastic-plastic range is defined by $(\rho-a)/(b-a) \times 100$ percent. After the fully-plastic state is reached, the stress distribution changes drastically as shown in the figure. The hoop stresses in the liner decrease slightly, but those in the jacket increase elastically as internal pressure is increased. Residual stress occurs only when the internal pressure p is larger than p^* ($= 176.6$ MPa). Finally, the distributions of hoop stresses before and after complete unloading are shown in Figure 4 for the original IMC as a comparison with the minimum-weight ECC.

REFERENCES

1. Witherell, M.D. and Scavullo, M.A., *Stress Analysis and Weight Savings of Internally Pressurized Composite-Jacketed Isotropic Cylinders*, Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology, Vol. 112, No. 4, pp. 397-403, November 1990.
2. Chen, P.C.T., *Residual Stresses in a Prestressed Steel Pressure Vessel Wrapped with Multilayered Composites*, Proceedings of the Sixth Technical Conference of American Society for Composites, pp. 980-989, October 1991.
3. Witherell, M.D., *Weight Reduction of Isotropic Cylinders Using Equivalent Compound Cylinders*, Proceedings of the Eighth International Conference on Composite Materials, ICCM/8, Honolulu, July 1991, paper 1-L.
4. Bland, D.R., *Elastoplastic Thick-Walled Tubes of Work-Hardening Material Subject to Internal and External Pressures and to Temperature Gradients*, Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol. 4, pp. 209-229, 1956.
5. Chen, P.C.T., *Stress and Deformation Analysis of Autofrettaged High Pressure Vessels*, ASME Pressure Vessels and Piping, Vol. 110, pp. 61-67, 1986.
6. Tsai, S.W., *Composite Design*, 3rd Edition, Think Composite, Dayton, OH, 1987.

Figure 1 Hoop strains as functions of internal pressure in the ECC and IMC.

Figure 2 Interface pressure and hoop stresses as functions of internal pressure in the ECC.

Figure 3 Distribution of hoop stresses before and after complete unloading in the ECC.

Figure 4 Distribution of hoop stresses before and after complete unloading in the IMC.

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